

ISOSTERIC HEATS OF ADSORPTION. PART I. ALCOHOLS ON SILICA GEL

By B. P. GYANI

The heats of adsorption of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *sec*-propyl, and *n*-butyl alcohols on silica gel have been measured at different fixed concentrations. This has been done by observing the variation in equilibrium pressures of the systems with temperature.

It is well known that substances of the same chemical group usually show similarity in the process of adsorption in the sense that the adsorption isotherms have the same general shape and can be brought together by adopting a suitable mode of plotting the data. It is therefore expected that such compounds should also show a comparable temperature dependence, and hence possess heats of adsorption of the same order. The heats of adsorption of methyl alcohol and its nearest homologues on silica gel have been measured with an intention to see how far this expectation is fulfilled, and are described below.

Two different experimental procedures are open for investigating this matter. We may either measure the heat evolved when the adsorbent takes up successive small quantities of the vapour directly in a calorimeter, or we may determine the equilibrium pressures for the same fixed quantity of the adsorbate and adsorbent present, and obtain the heat by means of the thermodynamic relation for reaction at constant volume. On the experimental side, the first method presents difficulties due to slow attainment of equilibrium, bad conductivity of the materials, and so on. During adsorption neither the volume nor the pressure is quite constant, and hence the heat measured is thermodynamically ill-defined (Kruyt and Moddermann, *Chem. Rev.*, 1930, 7, 259). The choice of temperatures has often been limited and measurements have commonly been made by the ice-calorimeter. These disadvantages are mostly overcome in the tensimetric method adopted here. By this method the measurements may be carried out both at increasing and decreasing temperatures with equal ease and precision.

EXPERIMENTAL

A tensimeter of simple design was constructed for these measurements. The form ultimately adopted is shown in Fig. 1. The adsorption bulb B containing some silica gel was sealed on to one limb of a U-tube manometer M. The gel was prevented from falling into the manometer, while handling the apparatus, by sealing in a small glass rod between the two constrictions at R. Another small bulb H was sealed on the other limb of M at about the same height as B. This side ended in a well ground glass tap T. Enough clean mercury was introduced into the manometer to fill about half the height on either side. The mercury was then collected in the bulb H by tilting the apparatus. The bulb was wrapped with a few folds of asbestos paper and heated with a small flame while the apparatus was being evacuated by means of a Cenco-Hyvac pump through T. When the evacuation was complete the tap T was closed and the bulb allowed to cool down. Some of the freshly distilled liquid under investigation was then introduced into the apparatus. The vapour was

rapidly taken up by the gel and the process was aided by cooling the bulb B. The excess liquid which condensed in B was heated to almost boiling and kept at that temperature for a few minutes to get rid of the adsorbed gases from the gel, not removed during evacuation. The excess was then pumped out, the tap T closed, and the mercury returned to the ma-

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

nometer. The apparatus was then clamped vertically in a large air thermostat. The tap was sealed with a few drops of mercury and painted on the sides with molten Faraday cement. The thermostat was maintained at temperatures constant to within one-tenth of a degree. The temperature regulation was by means of a simple mercury-toluene thermoregulator working in conjunction with an electro-magnetic relay. The heater was joined across the spark-gap in series with a variable resistance so that a residual current was always kept flowing through it. This current was adjusted in the usual way to balance the loss of heat to the surroundings as closely as possible.

The pressure was read directly on a meter scale attached rigidly to the manometer, to fractions of a mm. This arrangement enabled readings to be taken up to a temperature of 65° without any difficulty. Above this temperature the cement sometimes gave way suddenly when the experiment had to be stopped. After reaching the highest temperatures, often above 70°, the temperature was gradually lowered and another set of observations was recorded. The two sets of data were always in good agreement with each other.

After completing runs at an arbitrarily fixed constant composition, the tensimeter was taken out of the thermostat. The mercury was again collected in H in order to pump out an amount of vapour and the apparatus was reset for another run at a lower composition. The value of the composition *i. e.*, the amount of liquid present in the gel, was computed by reference to a previously determined isotherm at 35°.

The silica gel employed in these experiments was prepared by the author by mixing together under vigorous shaking equal volumes of dilute solutions of commercial hydrochloric acid (d 1.05) and sodium silicate (sp. gr. 1.12). The resulting sol required 3 to 4 hours to set to a stiff gel at the room temperature (about 30°). The raw gel was cut into pieces, washed free of electrolytes, and desiccated in gradual stages, finally in a current of dry air at 350° . The gel was a little opalescent. It was about two years old at the time of these measurements.

The measurements were performed with different quantities of the gel and some of them were checked up with a duplicate apparatus. One can therefore be sure that the results were not vitiated due to the presence of a small dead space inside the tensimeter, or non-uniformity of the gel.

The results of these observations are set down in the following tables. The first column gives the temperature T in degrees absolute, the second gives the pressure p in mm. of mercury. In the next two are recorded the values of $\log_{10} p$ and $1/T$ respectively. The next column shows the values of Q , the isosteric heat of adsorption, calculated as explained below. The pair of observations from which Q has been calculated is indicated in the sixth column. L , the latent heat of condensation of the vapour, is given at different temperatures where the vapour pressure data in the neighbourhood of that temperature are available in the literature

The van't Hoff expression for the heat of reaction at constant volume may be written as

$$\frac{d \log_{10} p}{d (1/T)} = \frac{Q}{2.303 \times R}$$

The value of the heat Q between any two temperatures T_1 and T_2 may be secured by taking the positive difference of the logs of the corresponding pressures p_1 and p_2 and dividing the result by the positive difference between $1/T_1$ and $1/T_2$, then multiplying the quotient by $2.303 \times R$. Alternatively, $\log p$ may be plotted against $1/T$. The slope of this curve is $Q/2.303 \times R$ from which Q may be calculated. The mean value of Q , obtained by either of these methods, may be checked up by the centre of gravity method or the more exact method of least squares, since the relation between $\log p$ and $1/T$ is linear when Q is constant.

TABLE I

Ethyl alcohol = 87.20×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.

T .	p .	$\log p$.	$1/T \times 10^4$.	Q calc. per mol.	Q obtained from	L calc. per mol'
299.3	43.0 mm.	1.6335	3347	11680	1,2	10070
307.7	73.0	1.8633	3250	12110	2,3	10140
312.6	99.0	1.9956	3200	11530	3,4	10140'
314.0	108	2.0334	3185	11700	4,5	10140
319.0	145	2.1614	3135	11200	5,6	10020
324.8	200	2.3010	3078	10650	6,7	9949'
328.5	240	2.3802	3044	11000	5,7	9949

TABLE I (contd.)

<i>T.</i>	<i>p.</i>	log <i>p.</i>	$1/T \times 10^4$	<i>Q</i> calc. per mol.	<i>Q</i> obtained from	<i>L</i> calc. per mol.
Ethyl alcohol = 83.28×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
804.5	56.0 mm.	1.7482	3284	11750	1,2	10140
818.8	100	2.0000	3186	11450	2,3	10020
820.7	148	2.1703	3118	11630	1,3	10020
812.0	93	1.8685	3200	11730	4,5	10140
815.8	113	2.0531	3167	11960	5,6	10020
818.0	129	2.1106	3145	10680	6,7	10020
824.4	181	2.2577	3082	11690	7,8	9949
826.7	206	2.3139	3060	10930	7,9	9949
Ethyl alcohol = 72.13×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
807.4	62.0	1.7924	3253	12280	1,2	10140
810.0	73.0	1.8633	3226	11820	2,3	10020
814.5	96.0	1.9823	3180	11050	3,4	9949
824.0	162	2.2095	3086	11840	4,5	9949
826.6	188	2.2742	3061	12110	5,6	9949
828.3	206	2.3139	3046	11930	4,6	9949
806.0	57.0	1.7559	3268	11130	1,7	10140
Ethyl alcohol = 59.4×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
804.3	46.0	1.6628	3286	13470	1,2	10140
806.7	54.5	1.7364	3261	11830	2,3	10140
808.8	62.5	1.7959	3238	11730	3,4	10140
817.4	104.5	1.0191	3151	10840	4,5	10020
823.5	145	1.1614	3091	10960	5,6	9949
827.0	174	1.2405	3058	10740	6,7	9949
829.5	197	1.2945	3035	10820	5,7	9949
Methyl alcohol = 51.44×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
816.0	13.0	2.1139	3165	9557	1,2	9200
823.1	18.2	2.2601	3095	9473	2,3	9200
826.3	211	2.3243	3064	11210	3,4	9200
829.1	243	2.3856	3039	10240	3,5	9200
Methyl alcohol = 41.83×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
803.0	42.0	1.6322	3300	9860	1,2	8976
812.5	69.9	1.8388	3200	10470	2,3	9221
821.5	108	2.0334	3115	10980	3,4	8904
825.5	137	2.1367	3072	10510	4,5	9215
829.2	164	2.2148	3038	10130	5,6	9215
830.7	177	2.2480	3023	10390	4,6	9215
Methyl alcohol = 23.97×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
803.5	5.5	0.7040	3284	12280	1,2	9221
810.7	8.8	0.9445	3219	11410	2,3	9221
816.7	12.0	1.0792	3165	12280	3,4	8904
822.2	17.5	1.2430	3104	11090	4,5	8904
826.4	22.0	1.3424	3080	13670	5,6	9215
829.7	27.0	1.4314	3033	11870	6,7	9215
834.2	34.5	1.5378	2992	12620	5,7	
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol = 59.55×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.						
804.5	20.0	1.3010	3284	12630	1,2	11440
811.0	31.0	1.4814	3215	12620	2,3	11440
815.3	41.0	1.6128	3171	12840	3,4	11170
820.5	57.0	1.7559	3120	11710	4,5	11170
825.8	77.0	1.8865	3069	11850	5,6	10960
828.8	91.0	1.9591	3041	10720	6,7	10960
832.5	108.5	2.0364	3008	11710	7,8	10960
836.1	132.1	2.1209	2975	11670	6,8	10960

TABLE I (contd.)

n-Propyl alcohol = 55.0×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.

T , °C.	p , mm.	$\log p$.	$1/T \times 10^4$	Q calc. per mol.	Q obtained from	L calc. per mol.
305.1	15.0	1.1761	3278	12280	1,2	11440
304.2	27.0	1.4314	3183	12780	2,4	11170
314.7	28.2	1.4502	3178	13300	3,5	11170
319.3	37.5	1.5740	3132	12840	4,5	11170
326.4	58.5	1.7672	3063	12700	5,6	10960
331.0	76.5	1.8837	3021	12770	4,6	10960

sec-Propyl alcohol = 27.24×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.

307.5	11.5	1.0007	3252	13620	1,2
313.0	17.0	1.2304	3195	13210	2,3
318.8	25.0	1.3979	3137	12580	3,4
322.8	32.0	1.5051	3098	13760	4,5
328.5	46.5	1.6675	3044	13550	5,6
333.0	61.5	1.7889	3003	13070	4,6

n-Butyl alcohol = 41.48×10^{-4} g. mol. per g. gel.

310.5	9.5	0.9823	3138	13710	1,2
317.4	11.0	1.0414	3151	14940	2,3
324.2	18.2	1.2001	3084	13300	3,4
332.5	31.0	1.4914	3008	14230	2,4

DISCUSSION

The values of $\log p$ have been plotted against $1/T$ in Figs. 2 and 3. It will be seen that

FIG. 3

the graphs are all rectilinear and the individual points rarely show any notable deviations. This means that there is no temperature variation of Q . This point is further discussed below.

Variation of Q with increasing Molecular Weight

The average values of Q for the various compounds at different concentrations are summarised in the following table. The figure under every compound gives its dipole moment in the usual units.

TABLE II

Substance.	x/m (g. mol. $\times 10^{-4}$)	Average Q , (calc./mol.).	Substance.	x/m (g. mol. $\times 10^{-4}$)	Average Q (calc./mol.).
Methyl alcohol 1.73	51.44	9223	<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol 1.65	59.55	12620
	41.83	9826		55.00	12778
	23.97	11470	<i>sec</i> -Propyl alcohol	27.24	13230
Ethyl alcohol 1.72	87.00	11520	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol 1.65	41.48	13970
	83.23	11570			
	72.13	11450			
	59.74	11530			
	40.80	11020			

Some general conclusions may be drawn from a study of this table. In the series of alcohols the heat of adsorption at comparable concentrations increases as the molecular weight is increased. The heat does not change much with increasing amount of adsorption but there is a general tendency for it to decrease as the concentration increases. In the case of ethyl alcohol, for example, Q is practically constant over a range of concentrations of about 60 to 87 g. mol. $\times 10^{-4}$ per g. of the gel. Data for the *n*- and *sec*-propyl alcohols were unfortunately not obtained at comparable concentrations, but it seems safe to conclude that the branching chain has no effect on Q when we take into account the increase in its value due to falling concentration.

Variation with Dipole Moment and Temperature

As far as these alcohols are concerned we note that the dipole moment decreases as the molecular weight is increased, but at the same time Q has a tendency to increase. The permanent dipole moment of the adsorbed molecules should therefore be considered as relatively unimportant in bringing about the attachment resulting in adsorption as far as the present systems are concerned. However, the permanent dipole moment is not the only important factor in physical attachment. The group of forces known as van der Waals forces collectively is made up of other forces also which may be equally or more important. Thus, in the case of two non-polar molecules, the total van der Waals interaction energy is given by

$$U = U_{\text{repulsion}} + U_{\text{dispersion}} + U_{\text{quadrupole}}$$

If the molecules in addition possess permanent dipoles, two new terms corresponding to their orientation and the induction produced by them would appear. None of these energy terms is directly dependent on temperature. It is therefore understandable that the measured values of Q show little variation with temperature.

The equation of Magnus (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, 141A, 270) for the heat of adsorption of a dipole or a quadrupole on a conducting surface is

$$\frac{q_0}{R} = c_k - (2/3) mT$$

where q_0 is the constant heat of adsorption in the beginning portion of the isotherm, R , the gas constant, and c_k and m are constants typical of the adsorbed molecule. Though silica gel is not a conductor, Kälbere and Schuster's measurements (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **142A**, 270) of the heat of adsorption of CO_2 on it are found to be in agreement with this equation. The present measurements often extend to a temperature range of 40° but the decrease in the value of Q , demanded by this equation, has not been noted in a single case. The decrease in the above cited case was about 25% of the total heat of adsorption and about 10% for the adsorption of water by charcoal, the increase in temperature being 40° . The present results are in agreement with most of the previous ones obtained by others with organic vapours on charcoal in this respect (Lamb and Coolidge and Pearce *et al.*, *vide infra*). The constancy of Q is remarkable in view of the fact that the latent heat of vaporisation decreases appreciably as the temperature is increased (see tables above).

Comparison with the Charcoal Data

The values of the heats of adsorption of organic vapours on charcoal, as obtained by Lamb and Coolidge (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1146) in an ice calorimeter are higher than those obtained in the present experiments in which the adsorbent is silica gel. The calorimetric and tensimetric measurements in general do not give identical results and the calorimetric values are as a rule higher, as shown by Pearce and his collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 1260; 1931, **35** 1091; 1935, **39**, 293). The values of Lamb and Coolidge correspond to a concentration of about 20×10^{-4} g. mol per g. of the charcoal and are contained in the following table.

TABLE III

Substance.	Present work.		Lamb & Coolidge.	
	Conc.	Q (tensimetric)	Conc.	Q (calorimetric)
Methyl alcohol	23.97	11470	20.0	13100
Ethyl alcohol	40.90	11920	20.0	15000

The present values of Q are clearly smaller than those of Lamb and Coolidge, but in view of the fact that the tensimetric method gives smaller values, one may conclude that each of the two alcohols on the two adsorbents has more or less equal values of Q . Evidently the equality will improve if the concentrations for the present values are reduced to be comparable with those of Lamb and Coolidge. One should also note that the measurements of these workers refer to a temperature of 0° , at which the vapours have a larger tendency to condense to a liquid. The whole matter merits further investigation.

Comparison with the Latent Heat of Condensation

One can see from Table I that the total heat of adsorption Q is always larger than L , the heat of condensation of the vapour to a liquid in bulk. Thus, the quantity $Q-L$ which has been called the net heat of adsorption (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1146) is always positive. The excess of Q over L can be explained if one assumes that the liquid in the adsor-

bed state is under compression. This postulate militates directly against the Kelvin equation or more directly the fundamental equation of capillarity

$$P = \sigma(1/R_1 + 1/R_2)$$

which requires that the liquid should exist under tension.

The net heat of adsorption is not always constant for different concentrations of the adsorbate except when the gel is fairly saturated. Even then the net heat is appreciable. Thus, it amounts to about 15% of the total Q for ethyl alcohol when x/m is in the range of 72 to 87 g. mol. $\times 10^{-4}$ per g. of the gel. For other alcohols it amounts to less than 10% at higher concentrations. At lower concentrations, the value shows a definite increase. It is 25% of the total Q when the gel has 60 and 24 units of x/m for ethyl and methyl alcohols respectively. The net heats of adsorption for carbon tetrachloride and chloroform are low, about 10% of the total Q , and almost constant as will be shown in a subsequent communication.

Although Q is always larger than L , one has to note that the two quantities are always of the same order of magnitude. The heat of reaction of some processes such as hydration of inorganic and organic materials, which is definitely chemical in nature, is also of the same order as has been pointed out by McBain ("Sorption of Gases and Vapours", p. 410, George Routledge and Sons, London, 1932). Condensation and hydration may be regarded as examples of purely physical and chemical processes respectively. The heat changes accompanying them "resemble corresponding values for sorption so strikingly that it is evident that all the reactions involved refer to generalisations which are wider than the scope of any purely physical or chemical conceptions. Stress cannot be laid upon a particular success in explaining data according to one special hypothesis without consideration of the whole general subject of chemical and physical interaction."

The author is grateful to Lt. Col. Sir C. P. N. Singh for his kind interest in this work. The author also thanks Professors S. Sugden and P. B. Ganguly for their many valuable criticisms.